

Investigating Principals' Competencies in Budgeting, Procurement, Internal Financial Control, and Financial Reporting in Kenyan Secondary Schools

Pius Kipruto Kosgei ^{#1}, Maphleba Lekhetho ^{*2}

^{1,2} Department of Educational Leadership and Management, University of South Africa, Pretoria, South Africa

Received: Sep 25, 2025

Accepted: Oct 21, 2025

Published: Dec 04, 2025

ABSTRACT

This study investigated principals' budgeting, procurement, internal financial control and financial reporting competencies as predictors of performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County, Kenya. Underpinned by agency theory as a theoretical framework, the study employed a quantitative methodology, utilising a correlational research design and questionnaires to collect data from principals and bursars. It used a multistage sampling technique to select a sample of 115 public secondary school principals and 111 school bursars. The findings and conclusions from the regression analysis are that the principals' financial reporting competencies (33.1%) were the major predictor of their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles, followed by principals' competencies in procurement (32%), internal financial control (24.4%), and finally, budgeting competencies (11.2%). This study further concluded that the principals' effective performance of selected financial management roles was explained by 86.3% of their budgeting, procurement, internal financial control and financial reporting competencies in Kajiado County. The study also concludes that other aspects of financial management, which were not studied, contributed to 13.7%. This study recommends that the MoE and other relevant agencies train, mentor and coach principals on identified competency and skills gaps and investigate other factors contributing to principals' ineffectiveness in financial management roles.

Keywords: Fiscal competencies, budgeting, procurement, internal financial control, financial reporting, performance of financial management roles

INTRODUCTION

Financial resource management is a vital issue in schools (County Education Board [CEB], 2019, 2022), particularly public secondary schools and a foundation of quality education services and sustainable school improvement efforts. In Kenya, the *Basic Education Act 2013* outlines a legal framework for financial management in basic education schools (Republic of Kenya, 2013), while the *Basic Education Regulations 2015* operationalise this act (Republic of Kenya, 2015c). The legal framework further facilitates the adoption of best practices in financial management to ensure quality educational outcomes and improve the effectiveness

and efficiency of deploying fiscal resources. Public secondary school principals are responsible for the financial management of their schools (Republic of Kenya, 2012b; 2013; 2017). Hence, they require specific fiscal competencies to perform financial management roles effectively and efficiently. Principals need specific skills in financial management for generating revenue, successful financial planning, school needs assessment and financial programming (Migwi, 2018).

In a study conducted in government primary schools in Damot Pulasa Woreda, South Ethiopia, Tadiwos (2014) found that principals lacked adequate skills in budget preparation and the engagement of BoM and other stakeholders in various financial activities. Similarly, Berhanu's (2018) study in Hadiya Zone public secondary schools found that principals faced challenges in procurement of works, had inadequate skills in financial management and lacked teamwork within the school management and other education structures. These skills shortages were linked to inadequate fund use and financial control training. In a study investigating principals' roles in financial management at public schools in the North West Province, South Africa, Mothibi (2015) concluded that some schools had no budgets or were poorly prepared, even if they did exist, and most schools lacked variance reports.

In Kenya, numerous complaints and discontent have been expressed regarding the principals' management of school finances (County Education Board [CEB], 2022), as most of them are unable to follow public financial accounting guidelines (Ministry of Education [MoE], 2017). Despite government funding, most public secondary schools still lack adequate instructional resources (Kosgei, 2018; Kosgei & Lekhetho, 2025).

Various studies have been conducted on the financial management of secondary schools. For instance, Mgendi et al.'s (2017) study of factors influencing principals' financial management capacity in Kaloleni and Rabai sub-counties' public secondary schools revealed ineffective performance of fiscal management roles. This ineffectiveness in financial management functions is prevalent in many counties nationwide (Wango & Gatere, 2016). Moreover, various education stakeholders in Kajiado County have raised concerns about the ineffective performance of some principals in financial management functions (Buchichi et al., 2018). These concerns include principals' low compliance with procurement and accounting regulations, as well as the BoM (Mulatya, 2022). The Directorate of Schools' audit report (County Education Board [CEB], 2022) indicated that some schools in Kajiado County submitted their books of accounts to the county schools' auditor late, while some financial records were poorly prepared and reported, with many principals lacking the requisite financial management skills and competencies. No study has investigated the relationship between the principals' fiscal competencies and their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles in Kenyan public secondary schools, particularly in Kajiado County. Hence, this research sought to fill this gap by determining principals' fiscal competencies as predictors of effectiveness in performing budgeting, procurement, financial internal control and financial reporting roles.

Objective of the Study

The study aims to establish principals' competencies in budgeting, procurement, internal financial control, and financial reporting as predictors of performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County, Kenya.

Research Hypothesis

The following are the research hypotheses of the study:

H01: There is no statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in budgeting and the adequate performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County.

H02: There is no statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in procurement and the adequate performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County.

H03: There is no statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in internal financial control and the adequate performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County.

H04: There is no statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in financial reporting and the adequate performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County.

Problem Statement

Public secondary schools in Kenya, particularly in Kajiado County, face a widespread issue of ineffective financial management performance (County Education Board [CEB], 2022; Ministry of Education, 2017; Phylisters et al., 2018). Principals are responsible for financial management, which includes budgeting, procurement, internal financial controls, and financial reporting (Republic of Kenya, 2012b; 2013; 2017). They also ensure financial accountability and transparency, and delegate financial responsibility to school bursars or accounts clerks. However, various education stakeholders often complain about the ineffectiveness of principals in performing certain financial management functions in public secondary schools in Kajiado County (County Education Board [CEB], 2022). Their ineffectiveness in performing budgeting, procurement, internal financial control, and financial reporting functions causes schools to suffer from financial losses. This study sought to establish principals' budgeting, procurement, internal financial control and financial reporting competencies as predictors of performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County and determine whether their ineffectiveness in executing financial management functions is related to the selected financial management competencies.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is underpinned by the agency theory, propounded by Ross and Mitnick in 1973 (Mitnick, 2024). Agency theory is a framework for evaluating the work performed by an agent (i.e., an employee) on behalf of a principal (i.e., an employer) (Laher & Proffitt, 2020). It describes the way workers behave in an organisation or their organisational behaviours, resulting from the relationship between the manager serving as the company's "agent" and the shareholder as the "principal" (Zogning, 2017). Workers have a utility maximization logic, meaning they seek the maximum benefit from the organisation even if their actions are not in their best interests. Agency theory explains the important relationships between principals and agents who act on their behalf. An agency relationship involves a contract through which the principal hires the agent to perform work on their behalf, granting them the authority to make decisions (Zogning, 2017). In this context, the Kenyan government has given school principals the power to manage their schools' finances.

The agency theory helps explain the actions of various interest groups in the corporate governance debate (Felin & Foss, 2023). The main attributes of this theory are the principal-agent relationship, information asymmetry, goal divergence, monitoring and control, and contracting (Vargas-Hernández, 2020). Information asymmetry is a feature of the principal-agent relationship, meaning the principal needs to learn more about the agent's actions or how they will turn out. A firm is seen as a nexus of contracts where the relationship between the principal and agent is contractual (Mitnick, 2024). The theory plays an important role in explaining the behaviour of school principals and the expectations of the BoM, MoE and TSC. This study identified performance of financial management as a goal conflict issue (an agency issue), which needs to be addressed by the agent through acquisition and implementation of various competencies in budgeting, procurement, financial internal control and financial reporting as they perform their respective financial management roles.

Reducing Agency Conflicts and Applying Theory in Financial Management

Agency theory emphasizes that the principal (the BoM, MoE, and TSC) and agent (school principals) should reduce the likelihood of conflict emergence by upholding the following actions and principles (Xiangyu, 2021). First, the transparency between the agent and the principal aims to reduce the potential influx of agency problems. To achieve this, the principal (BoM, TSC, and MoE) and the agent (school principal) must be fully transparent with one another (Felin & Foss, 2023). Second, they should impose restrictions or abolish negative restrictions to significantly reduce the effect of agency loss. Setting specific restrictions on factors such as agency power allows the principal to feel more confident in their agent (Mitnick, 2024). Similarly, abolishing negative restrictions instils trust within the agent and allows them to make decisions freely on behalf of the principal (Wang, 2024).

The third action, introducing and eradicating incentives and bonuses, reduces the chances of conflicts and disagreements. Introducing bonuses motivates an agent and encourages them to make decisions in the principal's best interests to achieve their desired incentives. In contrast, bonuses may motivate the agent to make decisions just for financial gain or achieve the incentive, disregarding the principal's best interests (Mitnick, 2024). As the principal or employer, the Kenyan government, through the BoM, TSC, and MoE, should create incentives for school principals as their agents to encourage them to comply with the requirements of the PFM Act 2012, the Basic Education Act 2013, PPADA 2015, and the Public Audit Act 2015 willingly.

Fourth, the principal may take strategic steps to limit the damage the agent's self-interested behaviour can cause (Laher & Proffitt, 2020). Common approaches to minimise conflict include defining job expectations and writing contracts to encourage the desired behaviour while limiting deviant and costly behaviours. Other strategies may include performance incentives, including rewards for good performance and sanctions for poor performance. Finally, the principal may wish to hire a third party to monitor or sample the agent's actions, such as hiring auditors (Felin & Foss, 2023). As the principal, the MoE hires school auditors and deploys education officials to monitor the school principals' work, aiming to improve their performance and minimise misappropriation and financial misconduct.

Weaknesses of Agency Theory

One of the main drawbacks of agency theory is that it assumes individuals act rationally, which may not always be the case (Laher & Proffitt, 2020). School principals as agents may not necessarily act in the best interests of their employers (the BoM, MoE, and TSC).

Principals' Competencies in Budgeting

The right financial management competencies can help principals manage their schools' financial activities. Such competencies include budget preparation, management, analysis, and procurement (Lipham, 2016). As accounting officers, principals must promote fiscal efficiency, effectiveness, and accountability in financial resource management to achieve the school's purpose and aim (MoE, 2017). This role requires principals to execute various financial management competencies effectively and efficiently.

Principals require specific skills to manage static or flexible school budgets (Nyakanyanga, 2019). Static budgets remain fixed during the budget life and all accounts and figures calculated initially remain the same regardless of ensuing variances (Ogbonnaya et al., 2017). Static budgets assess the effectiveness of the initial budgeting process. By contrast, flexible budgets have relational value to certain variables used in their derivation (Ogbonnaya et al., 2017). The figures in a flexible budget may vary depending on school enrolment changes, consumption patterns and economic variables. A flexible budget allows for variations when the assumptions used to formulate the budget change. Flexible budgets permit greater flexibility to changing circumstances, resulting in fewer budget variances, both positive and negative (Wasiche et al., 2018). However, fixed and flexible budgets are valuable to the school management.

Principals' Competencies in Procurement

Procurement involves “public schools’ acquisition by buying, hire, licence, rental, lease, franchise, tenancy or by any other contractual means of any type of goods, works or services using public resources or disposal of public assets” (Kenya Anti-Corruption Commission [KACC] & Public Procurement and Oversight Authority [PPOA], 2019). Public secondary schools in Kenya primarily allocate their funds and financial resources to procuring goods, services, or works.

Public secondary school principals need critical thinking skills to analyse procurement and financial data, and establish actions they should take when procuring goods, services, and works. Interpretation, observation, reflection, problem-solving, evaluation, and decision-making are important skills and competencies for principals to use to analyse financial facts and data to facilitate the selection of the best-fit suppliers (Embeli et al., 2014; Mebrate & Shumet, 2024).

Furthermore, principals need project management skills and competencies to execute procurement effectively in schools. They require them to manage procurement competently during the project cycles (Bakhshi et al., 2023). Project management skills are required in initiation, planning, execution, control and closing the project task as assigned by the school infrastructure committee (SIC) and the BoM. Moreover, principals need interpersonal skills to perform school procurement functions (Komakech & Machyo, 2015). This day-to-day life skill is used during communication and interaction with procurement stakeholders.

Principals require negotiation skills for procurement, as they often negotiate with suppliers during various procurement engagements. The outcome of procurement negotiations depends on the principals’ effectiveness in negotiating with suppliers (Embeli et al., 2014). In procurement, negotiation occurs when principals and their vendors, who have conflicting interests, reach an agreement. Procurement managers should develop contract management skills and competencies to empower procuring entities to be effective (Gray et al., 2021) and forge better supplier-vendor relationships. Contract management skills may further help

principals comply with the PPADA 2015, its PPAD 2020 regulations and guidelines to mitigate procurement risks

Furthermore, public secondary school principals require technological competencies and skills to perform procurement functions efficiently, including e-procurement. Adopting the right technology can help management drive value, become more efficient and effective in procurement, and make responsibilities more manageable (Neupane et al., 2022). Developing e-procurement proficiency and adopting and deploying ICT can empower procuring entities to monitor, manage, and maintain procurement tasks using tools, devices, and relevant procurement software (Faga, 2019). However, the inadequate technological skills of procurement officers and tender committee members undermine efforts to achieve effectiveness through the introduction of e-procurement (Dubey et al., 2019; Neupane et al., 2022).

Principals' Competencies in Internal Financial Control

With the right competencies in internal financial control, principals can establish appropriate policies, procedures, and activities to guide school financial management. An effective internal financial control system should include preventive and detective financial control procedures (Benkovic, 2018). Other financial control considerations include regular financial communication, financial policies and procedures, and reminders to staff members through emails, staff meetings, and other communication channels (Quak, 2020).

School principals should be skilled and competent in ensuring the electronic financial system has secure and sufficient software and hardware capabilities to protect financial data. The deployed financial system should be easily accessible to facilitate decision-making processes, and principals must secure digitised financial system and data (Rebs et al., 2018), mainly because digital financial records require secure access and retrieval capabilities (Hanif et al., 2018).

Furthermore, principals require appropriate skills and competencies to regularly evaluate financial risks and internal control systems, which are necessary to protect their schools' assets and records (Midialo, 2017). Risk management is a systematic process to continuously identify, assess, prioritise, control, monitor and document financial risk (Nyakarimi et al., 2020). Section 73(3)b of the PFM Act 2012 requires schools to conduct value-for-money, risk-based, and systems audits designed to strengthen internal financial control systems, thereby facilitating the achievement of strategic objectives within the entity, including schools. Regulation 165 (1) of the PFM Act requires accounting officers, such as principals, to develop a Risk-Based Assessment Framework (RBAF) and risk management strategies (Republic of Kenya, 2012a). These strategies include fraud prevention mechanisms and the development of financial risk management systems.

Principals' Competencies in Financial Reporting

The principal needs skills and competencies to produce budget reports. Each departmental head is responsible for their own budget in a school. Heads of departments require support from finance teams to track their budget requirements against planned budgets (Palepu et al., 2020). The principal and school financial management teams need skills and competencies to track planned departmental budgets against actual budgets implemented, capture commentaries from the heads of departments and communicate the budget status to the BoM through their reports. Such actions could enable financial managers to track budget implementation and monthly reports (Abang'a, 2017).

The principals' competencies in financial reporting are crucial to the success of financial operations. A school's financial reporting system presents school financial activities, processes the information into financial reports and communicates the findings to the school board. As Rupia and Chai (2022) suggested, school principals should have competencies and skills to prepare and present financial reports at each meeting of the BoM. The principal should table the balance sheets containing school creditors, a list of accruals, pre-payment and capital income and expenditure accounts to the school management (Shkurina, 2018). A project management report should be prepared and submitted if there are capital and infrastructure development projects like new constructions, extensions, new projects or major refurbishments and renovations in progress within the school. Rupavijetra et al. (2019) concluded that principals should be able to prepare and submit an annual report to various stakeholders showing income and expenditure for each capital project.

Principals' Performance of Budgeting

Principals perform budget and variance analyses (Ghorman & Amakyi, 2016). Therefore, they should prepare and present accurate budget analyses and strategic proposals to ensure budget stability (Radzi et al., 2018). Principals analyse budget variance against the budget forecast in performing financial management (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2017). They also use the budget to control activities to be implemented in the school. The actual spending in the school can be compared to the budgeted figures, which provide more clarification on actual spending (Ghorman & Amakyi, 2016), thereby offering better control over finances. This technique helps the principal and school management to use funds efficiently and judiciously. Effective budgeting may provide accurate financial information that helps the school to adjust, analyse and evaluate programmes and activities (Mohamad & Ibrahim, 2017).

Departmental budgets motivate staff to participate and focus on achieving departmental objectives. A clear focus also challenges and motivates them to stay within the budget limits and avoid overspending. Budgeting may help the principal and school management prioritise the projects or programmes to be undertaken (Ikediugwo, 2016). It helps identify feasibility, affordability, future funding requirements and project outcomes (Krishnan & Fashid, 2019). Budgeting may also help in the strategic allocation of school funds.

Principals track budgets in real-time, and as such, Hanif et al. (2018) advise that they should not wait until the end of the month, term, or year to track their spending. Reliance on retrospective school spending risks overspending and hurting the cash flow. Poor spending visibility also limits principals and finance teams from using a reactive strategy. Principals must regularly update their budget team members, especially since financial circumstances can change during the financial period, necessitating budget adjustments (Palepu et al., 2020). This situation requires regular analysis and adjustment of the budget for a healthy cash flow and financial stability. As Krishnan and Fashid (2019) stressed, to ensure financial spending is on track, budgets can be updated accordingly to improve budget execution. Radzi et al. (2018) argue that principals can utilize the data and results of the current budget to make more informed decisions for future budgeting. They can improve their existing budget strategies by optimising future scenarios. Principals can do this accurately and confidently if they have reliable, accurate, and timely data.

Performance of the Procurement Function

The operational requirements, department-specific programmes or project requirements and inventory data ought to guide development of a procurement plan (Ahsan & Paul, 2018). The principal should provide the latest market survey data to corroborate previous procurement profiles during procurement planning, facilitating the preparation of realistic and accurate plans. The procurement profile typically includes goods, works and services, their cost, and the procurement methods used (Komakech & Machyo, 2015), including vendor information, geographical location and the importance of goods, works or services to school operations.

Procurement managers perform project management roles that are invaluable for executing procurement in their schools (Wankmüller & Reiner, 2021), encompassing the initiation, planning, execution, control, and closure of project procurement (Bakhshi et al., 2023). Project management requires principals to use their skills, knowledge, and techniques to implement projects efficiently and effectively.

As buyers, principals relate with vendors for various business deals and should negotiate during the procurement process. The outcome of the procurement deal depends on how effectively procuring entities negotiate with vendors (Paciarroti et al., 2021). It is essential to negotiate effectively with suppliers who have conflicting requirements to agree on issues of mutual interest (Beal Partyka, 2022). The procurement negotiation process aims to secure five key rights: the right price, time, location, right goods, works, or services, and quantity, to ensure procurement sustainability (Rebs et al., 2018). Strategic procurement enables principals to identify the optimal mix of goods, works, and services that support the school's procurement objectives. Managers analyze high-volume procurement and develop long-term partnerships with suppliers who provide high-quality goods, works, and services at low costs (Paciarrotti et al., 2021).

E-procurement broadens access to quality goods, works, or services, and enables schools to save on procurement costs (Dubey et al., 2018) and utilise public financial resources more efficiently. The benefits of transitioning to e-procurement include lowered cost of advertising, vendor access, bid document distribution, and improved bidders' access to tendering opportunities (Faga, 2019). E-procurement enhances the competitiveness of quotations and fosters stronger commercial relationships between vendors and procuring institutions (Dubey et al., 2019). According to Dubey et al. (2019), principals engage in contract management during procurement, which enhances the effectiveness of procurement functions and fosters strong relationships between clients, suppliers and vendors. In Kenya, contract management helps enforce compliance with the PPADA 2015, regulations, and guidelines, thereby mitigating procurement risks (Public Procurement Oversight Authority [PPOA], 2015).

Performance of the Internal Financial Control Function

In Greek state schools, principals are responsible for developing and maintaining internal financial control frameworks to achieve the schools' objectives efficiently, effectively and accountably (Argyropoulou, 2009). In Serbian public schools, finance managers employ financial risk management methods to identify and assess financial risks and utilize cost-benefit analysis in developing internal financial controls (Benkovic, 2018). The principal and the BoM should manage adequate financial risks by implementing effective internal controls.

Managers can execute financial risk management by developing an effective financial system and internal financial control framework (Hanoon et al., 2021). This system enables management to establish, document, implement, utilize, maintain, and comply with the

school's internal financial controls (Lai et al., 2020). A financial system should be accessible to all school departments and employees responsible for using it, as well as those responsible for ensuring adherence to internal financial controls (Okeze et al., 2018).

The separation of duties within a function, department, or school should be implemented such that an individual does not process payments from start to finish. Ghorman and Amakyi (2016) emphasise that duties should be segregated in financial processes, including custody of school assets, authorisation of financial activities, and recording of transactions. The inadequate or absence of segregation of duties can lead to the misappropriation of assets and the misstatement of financial statements (Radzi et al., 2018).

The principal should safeguard school assets by storing, locking and securing them. Rupavijetra et al. (2019) recommended that school authorities store cash in a secure location with restricted access, such as a fireproof safe, and control access to financial data and other assets. The school's financial information system should adopt user identities and unique passwords that are frequently changed by the system (Onesmo, 2021).

Automation and process optimisation by the principal is essential for proper internal financial controls. Automation and process optimisation tools enable schools to adopt, develop, implement and enforce financial internal controls (Ghorman & Amakyi, 2016). Principals can use these safeguards in vendor relationship management, contract management and adopting supply chain optimisation tools to minimise embezzlement, risk of fraud, and haphazard spending and to support guided buying (Ikediugwo, 2016).

Performance of Financial Reporting Function

Roje and Redmayne (2021) defined financial reporting as the process of producing financial accounts that disclose a school's fiscal position to management, stakeholders, and the government. A financial reporting system utilises user-friendly formats to present fiscal information to relevant stakeholders for decision-making. It involves financial reports that include internal reports, the BoM, and the creditors' reports.

The principal may use financial reports to improve debt management, as debt can lead to litigation against the school by creditors and hinder its operations and progress. Different types of financial reports are classified according to purpose or software (Rupia & Chai, 2022). Financial reports provide principals with the opportunity to track financial activities in real-time. They enable schools to manage liabilities, which constitute a critical part of their financial health (Nguyen & Truong, 2017). Financial reports enable principals to manage suppliers' expectations and improve vendor relationships (Dubey et al., 2018).

Financial reporting enables principals to communicate clearly and allows stakeholders to access financial data for their schools. Hence, financial managers should make analysed financial reports accessible to many devices (Glover, 2018). Shkurina (2018) emphasized that principals can quickly respond to financial challenges by improving internal communication across departments and stakeholders, who have unfettered access to important financial data, information, and insights within the school.

Financial reports enable principals to mobilise resources and perform school audits, which assist them in coordinating the mobilisation of funds from government and non-state actors. They can also facilitate mandatory audits (Robert et al., 2021). School auditors audit financial statements and records of all public secondary schools and express their opinions. Financial reports are crucial for making accurate projections and developing predictive strategies (Deis

& Shroff, 2020). Financial management reporting tools can provide comprehensive and insightful information on financial performance and processes. Real-time, predictive, and historical financial data provide a snapshot of information that can help school principals and other users enhance accuracy in forecasts based on previous or emerging trends (Amos & Koda, 2018).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a positivist paradigm, which relies on measurement and reason and assumes that knowledge emerges from a neutral, measurable, or quantifiable observation of activity, action, or reaction (Silverman, 2021). Consequently, it employed a quantitative methodology to measure quantity or amount (Wallen & Fraenkel, 2019). In quantitative research, diverse numerical data is collected through various methods and analysed statistically to aggregate, compare, or show relationships among the data. Quantitative data is generally collected through questionnaires, structured observations and experiments (Bingham & Witkowsky, 2022). The results from quantitative methods may be generalised to broader populations based on the sampling methods used.

This study adopted a correlational research design, which involved measuring the principals' fiscal competencies in budgeting, procurement, internal financial control and financial reporting without trying to control or manipulate the variables (Putri et al., 2025). It further measured their effectiveness in performing financial management functions, evaluated their strengths and the direction of the relationship, and established the contribution of each independent variable to the dependent variable while controlling for the other variables. The design enabled the researcher to conduct an in-depth study of selected financial management competencies with minimal effort, time and financial resources.

Target Population

The study targeted all public secondary school principals and their bursars who were responsible for budgeting, procurement, internal financial control, and financial reporting. It included the school bursars to facilitate data triangulation and validate inferences from multiple sources. The study's accessible population was all 160 principals performing administrative duties in public secondary schools in Kajiado County (TSC records, January 2023) and their 160 bursars (CDE's office, 2023). The researcher had easy access to these respondents, as they were on duty, willing, and available to participate in the study.

Sampling Procedure

This research employed multistage sampling to identify principals and bursars as respondents, utilizing various sampling techniques at different stages. Principals were stratified into male and female categories, while schools were stratified into girls', boys', and mixed boarding, mixed day, and mixed day and boarding schools. The study adopted proportionate sampling to establish proportionate samples of principals for each data stratum. A survey was used to identify and include school bursars from all the sampled schools.

Questionnaires

The questionnaires were used to gather data from principals and bursars, as Silverman (2021) explained that they are ideal for measuring a particular viewpoint. The questionnaires targeted each research variable in each hypothesis. The two questionnaire sets contained identical items to facilitate data triangulation from principals and bursars. The study adopted a Likert-type questionnaire with a 4-point rating scale. Removing the midpoint in a 5-point Likert scale

provided differentiated responses and encouraged respondents to provide clearer-cut answers. A 4-point Likert scale captures respondents' perceptions and opinions on services they have experienced or used (Richter et al., 2022).

Validity and Reliability of Research Instruments

Instrument validation assesses the ability of a data collection tool to accurately measure what it is intended to measure (De Vellis, 2016). Data collection instruments were constructed based on the research objectives to establish content validity. To establish construct validity, the researcher operationalised the variables of interest: the principals' fiscal competencies in budgeting, procurement, internal financial control, financial reporting, and effective performance of selected management roles. The researcher also clearly defined a target population to establish external validity and carefully selected a representative sample. External validity refers to the extent to which the findings of one study are generalisable to the broader population with similar research attributes (Hair et al., 2016). To address internal validity, the respondents were selected randomly to ensure they represented the target population. While piloting the research instruments, the researcher adopted a test-retest method to investigate their external reliability.

DATA ANALYSIS

The study employed inferential statistical analysis for quantitative data, enabling the researchers to draw inferences from the data analysis. Data is analysed to clean, inspect, model, and transform it to highlight important inferences to support the decision-making process (Howard & Nitzl, 2020). The researchers tested and analyzed each research hypothesis, and subsequently performed regression analysis to establish a regression model, regression coefficients and a regression equation.

Hypothesis Testing

The researcher set the study's judgement to either reject or fail to reject the null hypotheses at the 0.05 alpha level; that is, reject H_0 : if $p < 0.05$, otherwise fail to reject H_0 : if $p > 0.05$. The first null hypothesis tested in this section was **H01**: "There is no statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in budgeting and effective performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County, Kenya". To test this hypothesis, a correlation analysis was conducted between principals' competencies in budgeting and the effective performance of selected financial management roles in Kajiado County. Table 1 presents the correlation test result.

Table 1: Correlation between Principals' Competencies in Budgeting and their Performance of Financial Management Roles

		Principals' performance of financial management roles
	Pearson Correlation r	.703**
Budgeting competencies	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	106

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient test yielded a result of ($p=0.703^*$; $p<0.05$) at an alpha level of 0.05, as shown in Table 1. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected since the p-value (0.000) is less than the 0.05 alpha level. This result indicates a positive and statistically significant relationship between principals' budgeting competencies and their performance in financial management roles in Kajiado County. In their study, Amos and Koda (2018) found that school principals' skills in preparing budget estimates are important in directing financial resources to acquire teaching and learning resources. This finding suggests that the effective performance of financial management roles can be enhanced when principals possess the necessary skills and competencies in budgeting.

The second null hypothesis tested in this section was **H02**: "There is no statistically significant relationship between principals' competencies in procurement and effective performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County, Kenya". The correlation test result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between Principals' Competencies in Procurement and Their Performance of Financial Management Roles

		Principals' performance of financial management roles
Principals' competencies in procurement	Pearson Correlation r	.876**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	106

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient test yielded $r=0.876^*$; $p<0.05$ at alpha 0.05 level as Table 2 displays. As such, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis since the p-value (0.000) is less than the 0.05 alpha level. This result indicates a positive and statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in procurement and their performance of financial management roles. This finding demonstrates that the effective performance of identified financial management roles could improve when principals possess the necessary skills in procurement.

The third null hypothesis tested in this section was **H03**: "There is no statistically significant relationship between principals' competencies in internal financial control and effective performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County, Kenya". Table 3 displays the correlation test result.

Table 3: Relationship between Principals’ Competencies in Internal Financial Control and Effective Performance of Selected Financial Management Roles

			Principals’ performance of financial management roles
Internal financial control competencies	Pearson	Correlation r	.885**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	106

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient test yielded a result of $r = 0.885$; $p < 0.05$ at an alpha level of 0.05, as shown in Table 3. Consequently, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis since the p-value (0.000) is less than the 0.05 alpha level. The results show a positive and statistically significant relationship between principals’ internal financial control competencies and their performance in financial management roles. This result corroborates Hanoon et al.’s (2021) finding that the benefits that accrue from the implementation of internal controls are immense. This finding established that effective performance of financial management roles could improve when principals possess the necessary skills in internal financial control.

The fourth and final null hypothesis tested in this section was **H04**: “There is no statistically significant relationship between principals’ competencies in financial reporting and effective performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajjado County.” Table 4 presents the correlation test result.

Table 4: Relationship between Principals’ Competencies in Financial Reporting and Effective Performance of Selected Financial Management Practices

			Principals’ Performance of Financial Management Practices
Financial reporting competencies	Pearson	Correlation r	.880**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	106

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient test yielded $r=0.880$ *; $p<0.05$ at an alpha level of 0.05, as indicated in Table 4. Hence, the researcher rejected the fourth and final null hypothesis since the p-value (0.000) was less than the 0.05 alpha level. This indicates a positive and statistically significant relationship between principals’ financial reporting competencies and their performance in financial management roles. Similarly, Ge et al. (2021) and Gray et al. (2021) concluded that finance management staff must possess advanced skills in developing and deploying key financial reporting tools, including income statements, balance sheets, financial statements, and statements of cash flows. The outcome highlights that the

performance of financial management can improve when principals possess the necessary skills in financial reporting.

Regression Analysis

This section presents regression analysis, including the assumptions of the regression model and its tests, the regression model summary, ANOVA, multicollinearity tests, and coefficient tables. The researcher performed a regression analysis to establish the predictive ability of independent variables on the dependent variable. The principals' fiscal competencies — budgeting, procurement, internal financial control, and financial reporting — were the independent variables of the study, while the dependent variable was the performance of financial management functions. The dependent variable addressed the principals' performance of budgeting, procurement, internal financial control, and financial reporting roles. The regression analysis findings are presented in the subsequent section.

Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) uses two or more independent variables to predict the value of a dependent variable (Schuberth et al., 2020). Gray et al. (2021) further explain that MLR is a statistical method and technique used to determine a mathematical relationship between multiple random variables. More specifically, it examines the relationship between several independent variables and one dependent variable. Richter et al. (2022) argued that data analysts may use this technique to find the model's variation and the relative contributions of each independent variable to the overall variance. To determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the researcher conducted a multiple linear regression analysis. Testing of assumptions for the regression model, model summary table, ANOVA, and the regression model were done, presented and discussed.

Assumptions and Testing the Assumptions of the Regression Analysis

Some assumptions must be met for the regression model to be relevant (Podsakoff et al., 2012). Violation of the model's assumptions yields inefficient, biased, or misleading forecasts, confidence intervals, or scientific insights. This study made the following five primary assumptions about the regression model:

1. The model has the absence of heteroskedasticity or the presence of homoscedasticity.
2. Independent variables are independent and were observed with negligible error.
3. There is a linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables.
4. There is an absence of autocorrelation in the residuals from the regression model's output.
5. There is an absence of multicollinearity.

Various tests were done to test the model assumptions. These included heteroskedasticity testing, testing for the independence of errors, a linearity test, the Durbin-Watson test, and a test for multicollinearity. These tests are explained further in the following section.

Heteroskedasticity

Heteroskedasticity refers to a situation where the variance of the residuals varies across a range of measured values (Noble & Smith, 2015; Silverman, 2021). The existence of heteroskedasticity implies that the population used in the regression contains unequal variance. The existence of heteroskedasticity in the analysis may invalidate the results (Noble & Smith, 2015). If the results of the tests are above the significance level ($p > 0.05$), then it is concluded that the data in the variable is normal, and vice versa (Bingham & Witkowsky, 2022). A Breusch-Pagan test statistic was used to test the following null hypothesis:

H01: Homoscedasticity is present in the data, and **H0:** There is no heteroskedasticity in the data. Table 5 presents the results.

Table 5: Modified Breusch-Pagan Test for Heteroskedasticity^{a,b,c}

χ^2	df	Sig.
2.858	1	.091

- a. Dependent variable: Principals' performance of financial management roles
- b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.
- c. Predicted values from design: Intercept + IV1 + IV2 + IV3 + IV4

IV1 is the principal's competencies in budgeting, IV2 is the principal's competencies in procurement, IV3 is the principal's competencies in financial internal control and IV4 is the principal's competencies in financial reporting in public secondary schools in Kajiado County.

The findings in Table 5 show a $\chi^2(1) = 2.858, p > 0.05$. Accordingly, this study fails to reject the null hypothesis and concludes that homoscedasticity exists in the data set. This finding implies that the residuals are distributed with equal variance. This finding implies that the regression model is dependable. The heteroskedasticity in the data makes the regression model less reliable (Sarstedt et al., 2022).

Testing for Independence of Errors

It is important to test for independence of errors because the absence of independence can lead to biased estimates of the regression coefficients. This situation can lead to incorrect inferences about the relationships between the variables (Hair et al., 2020; Podsakoff et al., 2012). Figure 1 illustrates the finding.

Figure 1: Testing for Independence of Errors

When testing for independence of errors, there should be no pattern or structure in the lag plot if the errors are independent (Hair et al., 2016). The points will appear to be randomly scattered across the plot, as shown in Figure 1, indicating no significant dependence on the errors.

Linearity Test

Scatter plots can be used to test the linearity assumption. This test is used to determine whether all linear regression models between a dependent variable and an independent variable are related to a straight line, or a line with a positive slope, to the right or at the bottom right (Ramli et al., 2018).

Figure 2: Linearity Test

Figure 2 indicates that the data points follow the regression line, suggesting that each predictor variable and the response variable have a linear relationship.

Durbin-Watson Test

The Durbin-Watson statistic detects autocorrelation in the residuals from the regression model’s output. The significance of autocorrelated disturbances is that the t, F, and χ^2 d distributions are invalid (Sarstedt et al., 2019). This statistic implies that estimation and prediction of the regression vector are inefficient. Table 6 presents the results.

Table 6: Durbin-Watson

Model	Durbin-Watson
1	1.711

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Budgeting competencies, principals’ competencies in procurement, financial internal control competencies, and financial reporting competencies
- b. Dependent Variable: Principals’ performance of financial management roles

The Durbin-Watson statistic is 0-4, with an acceptable range of 1.50 - 2.50. A value of 2 or nearly 2 indicates no first-order autocorrelation (Schuberth et al., 2020). In instances where successive error differences are slight, the Durbin-Watson is low (less than 2.50). The assumption was therefore passed, as the statistical value fell within the acceptable range.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test assessed whether there were high intercorrelations among two or more independent variables in the multiple regression model. Very high intercorrelations or

inter-associations among independent variables indicate multicollinearity (Sarstedt et al., 2019). This situation can result from an approximate linear relationship among some of the predictor variables in the study. This type of disturbance in the dataset renders statistical inference unreliable (Cohen et al., 2018).

Variance inflation factor (VIF) detects and measures the extent of collinearity in a multiple regression model (Ketokivi, 2019). VIF measures the extent to which the variance is inflated when the predictor variables are linearly related in the estimated regression coefficients, compared to when they are not (Cohen et al., 2018). The variables with high VIF indicators make the regression model unreliable in predicting the dependent variable (Sarstedt et al., 2019). This study tested multicollinearity by calculating tolerance and its reciprocal, the VIF. Table 7 displays these results.

Table 7: Multicollinearity Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Budgeting competencies	.505	1.980
Principals' Competencies in Procurement	.219	4.556
Financial Internal Control Competencies	.201	6.446
Financial Reporting Competencies	.204	4.912

a. *Dependent Variable: Principals' performance of financial management roles*

According to Ketokivi (2019), multicollinearity occurs when two or more predictors are correlated. The presence of multicollinearity in the multiple regression model increases the standard error of the coefficients. This situation implies that by over-inflating the standard errors, multicollinearity makes some variables in the model statistically insignificant when they should be significant. According to Sarstedt et al. (2019), VIFs greater than 10 give some cause for concern. The results associated with multiple regression analysis are known to be adversely affected by high levels of VIF.

The data in Table 5.74 show that the VIF values for the four predictors lie within the acceptable range of less than 10 ($VIF < 10$). Similarly, the simultaneous tolerance values were in the acceptable range of above 0.2. This result shows that the coefficients, and hence, the variables were stable and independent of each other and were not collinear. Consequently, the absence of multicollinearity makes the adopted multiple regression model reliable. These results further imply that the principals' competencies in budgeting, procurement, internal financial control and financial reporting did not influence each other in determining their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles in Kajiado County.

Model Summary

The model summary statistics compare a specific model with another of the same kind. It can also indicate the model's relevance in predicting the dependent variable. Table 8 presents the summary results of the model.

Table 8: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.930 ^a	.866	.863	.29075

a. *Predictors: (Constant), Financial Reporting Competencies, Budgeting Competencies, Principals' Competencies in Procurement, Financial Internal Control Competencies*

The coefficient of determination (adjusted R²) measures the model's ability to explain the contribution of the independent variable to the dependent variable (Euginie & Eman, 2023). Coefficient values of determination range from 0 to 1. A value of R² closer to 1 indicates that the dependent variable explains almost all the variation in the independent variable (Hair et al., 2020). The R², being a metric of predictive ability, indicates that values closer to 1 suggest a higher predictive ability (Sarstedt et al., 2019). The findings in this model indicate that the R-squared value is 0.863, as shown in Table 8. According to the findings in the model summary, 86.3% of principals' competencies in budgeting, procurement, financial internal control and financial reporting indicated their effective performance of selected financial management roles. This result suggests that other variables outside the scope of this study may have contributed 13.7% to principals' effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles. This finding is significant because the model is highly robust ($R^2 = 0.863$) and can be applied to regression analysis.

ANOVA for Regression Model

ANOVA for a regression model indicates the degree of variability within the regression model and serves as the foundation for testing significance (Euginie & Eman, 2023). ANOVA can help determine the overall impact of a categorical predictor on the outcome and the interaction effect between two or more categorical predictors (Esser & Vliegenthart, 2017). Squared regression is the sum of the differences between the predicted value and the mean of the dependent variable. Table 9 presents the ANOVA results for the regression model.

Table 9: ANOVA^a for Regression Model

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	109.567	4	27.392	324.021	.000 ^b
	Residual	16.992	201	.085		
	Total	126.559	205			

a. Dependent Variable: Principals' Performance of Financial Management Roles

b. Predictors: (Constant), Financial Reporting Competencies, Budgeting Competencies, Principals' Competencies in Procurement, Financial Internal Control Competencies

ANOVA was used to analyse the robustness of the model. The results show that the model is highly significant at the 0.05 alpha level, with $R^2 = 0.866$, $F(4, 201) = 324.021$, and $p < 0.05$, indicating that all predictors significantly contribute to the performance of the selected financial management roles.

Regression Coefficients

The regression coefficient is an analytical tool for determining the average functional relationship between variables. Esser and Vliegenthart (2017) explain that regression coefficients serve as multipliers for variables, facilitating the explanation of the correlation between an independent and dependent variable. The results of the regression analysis coefficients are presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
(Constant)	.197	.071		2.786	.006	.058	.337
Budgeting Competencies	.092	.030	.112	3.074	.002	.033	.151
Competencies in Procurement	.301	.052	.320	5.804	.000	.199	.403
Financial Internal Control Competencies	.212	.057	.244	3.712	.000	.100	.325
Financial Reporting Competencies	.304	.053	.331	5.780	.000	.200	.408

a. Dependent Variable: Principals’ performance of financial management roles

Based on the standardized coefficients, financial reporting competencies appear to be the major contributor to the principals’ effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles ($\beta_4 = 0.33$; $p = 0.000$). The findings also established that the principals’ competencies in procurement were the second most significant factor impacting their effectiveness in performing financial management roles ($\beta_2 = 0.320$; $p = 0.000$). Thirdly, financial internal control competencies have a significant impact on principals’ performance in financial management roles ($\beta_3 = 0.244$; $p = 0.000$). Finally, the results show that budgeting competencies ($\beta_1 = 0.112$; $p = 0.002$) contributed the least to principals’ effective performance in financial management roles in this research. The data in Table 10 show that the four predictors combined were statistically significant in predicting principals’ effective performance of financial management roles in Kajiado County public secondary schools ($t = 2.786$; $p < 0.05$).

Regression Equation

The following regression equation guided this study:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon$$

Where Y = Principals’ Performance of Financial management roles, β_0 = Constant, X_1 = Budgeting competencies, X_2 = Competencies in Procurement, X_3 = Financial Internal Control Competencies, and X_4 = Financial Reporting Competencies, and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3,$ and β_4 were the coefficients of independent variables.

The model equation of the study was presented as $Y = 0.197 + 0.112 X_1 + 0.32 X_2 + 0.244 X_3 + 0.331 X_4 + \epsilon$.

Interpreted as $Y=0.197+$ (Budgeting competencies*0.112) + (Competencies in Procurement*0.320) + (Financial Internal Control Competencies*0.244) + (Financial Reporting Competencies*0.331) and ϵ is the error term.

In this study, the regression equation coefficients indicated that a change in 1 unit in budgeting competencies could impact the principals’ effectiveness in performing financial management roles by 0.112 units. Similarly, a unit increase in competencies in procurement impacts the principals’ effectiveness in performing financial management roles by 0.320 units. Thirdly, a

unit increase in financial internal control competencies increases effectiveness in performing financial management roles by 0.244 units. Finally, it was evident that a unit increase in financial reporting competencies would lead to a 0.331-unit increase in effectiveness in performing financial management roles.

This finding established that financial reporting and procurement competencies contributed 33.1% and 32.0% to the principals' performance in financial management roles, respectively. Similarly, financial internal control and budgeting competencies contributed 24.4% and 11.2% respectively, to the principals' performance of financial management roles.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This section presents a summary of the key findings related to the four research hypotheses.

Summary of Key Findings Related to Research Hypotheses

The study's first hypothesis was **H01**: There is no statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in budgeting and the adequate performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County. The first significant finding is a positive and statistically significant relationship between the principals' budgeting competencies and their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles. This finding corroborates Amos and Koda's (2018) finding that principals' skills in preparing budget estimates were important in directing financial resources to acquire teaching and learning resources.

The second hypothesis of this study was **H02**: There is no statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in procurement and the adequate performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County. The second significant research finding is a positive and statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in procurement and their performance of selected financial management roles. Similarly, Wasiche et al. (2018) found that principals face various challenges, including inadequate financial management skills in sourcing required instructional resources, food items, services and works.

The third hypothesis of this study was **H03**: There is no statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in internal financial control and the effective performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County. In contrast, the study established a positive and statistically significant relationship between principals' internal financial control competencies and their performance of selected financial management roles. This result corroborates Hanoon et al.'s (2021) finding that implementing internal controls yields immense benefits, including reduced wastage, improvement in financial performance and overall organisational performance. This finding suggests that the effective performance of financial management roles can be improved if principals possess the necessary skills in financial internal control.

The fourth hypothesis of this study was **H04**: There is no statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in financial reporting and the adequate performance of selected financial management roles in public secondary schools in Kajiado County. However, the fourth major research finding indicated a positive and statistically significant relationship between principals' competence in financial reporting and their performance of selected financial management roles. This finding concurs with Ge et al.'s (2021) and Gray et al.'s (2021) conclusion that finance management staff must have advanced skills in developing and

deploying important financial reporting tools such as income statements, financial statements, cash flow statements, and balance sheets. This finding suggests that the effective performance of financial management roles can be enhanced when principals possess the necessary skills in financial reporting.

Summary of the Findings from the Regression Analysis

The regression analysis found that financial reporting competencies were the major predictors of principals' effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles (33.1%). The findings also show that principals' competencies in procurement are the second most significant predictor that impacted their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles (32%). Third, the study established that financial internal control competencies significantly impact the principals' effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles (24.4%). Finally, the study found that budgeting competencies (11.2%) contributed the least to the effective performance of selected financial management roles in this research.

The research findings indicate that effective performance of selected financial management roles is explained by 86.3% of principals' competencies in budgeting, procurement, internal financial control and financial reporting. This outcome suggests that other financial management aspects not addressed by this study contribute 13.7% of the factors that influence the principals' effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles.

CONCLUSIONS

This section presents a summary of conclusions related to the four research hypotheses.

Conclusions Relating to Research Hypotheses

The first conclusion is that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between principals' budgeting competencies and their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles. Similarly, Amos and Koda (2018) concluded that principals' skills in preparing budget estimates are crucial in directing financial resources to acquire teaching and learning resources, thereby improving learning outcomes in their schools.

The second conclusion is that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between the principals' competencies in procurement and the adequate performance of selected financial management roles. In their study, Wasiche et al. (2018) also concluded that some principals faced various challenges that included inadequate financial management skills in sourcing required instructional resources, food items, services and works. They found that most principals surveyed felt they needed more financial management capacity building in procurement to be effective.

The third conclusion is that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between principals' internal financial control competencies and the adequate performance of selected financial management roles. Similarly, Hanoon et al. (2021) concluded that effective implementation of internal controls yields immense benefits. They further concluded that principals require risk management skills to minimize waste and enhance financial performance.

The fourth major conclusion is a positive and statistically significant relationship between the principals' competence in financial reporting and the effective performance of selected financial management roles. Ge et al. (2021) and Gray et al. (2021) also concluded that finance

management staff must possess advanced skills in developing and deploying key financial reporting tools, including income statements, balance sheets, financial statements, and statements of cash flows.

Conclusions Relating to Regression Analysis

1. The regression analysis concluded that the principals' financial reporting competencies (33.1%) were the major predictor of their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles. The principals' competencies in procurement were the second most significant factor (32%) that impacted their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles. Third, the study concluded that principals' financial internal control competencies (24.4%) significantly impacted their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles. Another conclusion is that the principals' budgeting competencies were the least significant factor (11.2%) contributing to their effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles in this research.
2. This study further concluded that 86.3% of their competencies in budgeting, procurement, financial internal control and financial reporting in Kajiado County could explain the principals' effective performance of selected financial management roles.
3. Finally, this study concluded that other aspects of financial management not studied contributed some 13.7 % of the factors that affected the principals' effectiveness in performing selected financial management roles in Kajiado County. Other financial management elements, beyond the variables examined in this study, may explain these additional competencies or factors.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This section presents the recommendations based on the four hypotheses that this study investigated, followed by those proposed for policy actions and interventions by the MoE and teacher training institutions.

Recommendations Regarding Research Hypothesis 1

The following recommendations are proposed based on the study's findings and conclusions. First, the study recommends that the MoE train, mentor, and coach principals in budget preparation, use, and management. Principals should participate in in-service financial management training, especially in interpretation, to guide heads of department in budget-making. This enables them to link school development plans to the school budget and to regularly align budgets with vote heads.

Recommendations Regarding Research Hypothesis 2

The MoE, TSC, KEMI, and KESSHA could provide further training for principals on the preparation of procurement plans, procurement risk, and contract management to ensure that procurement rules are followed regularly, enhance supply sustainability, utilize and reuse vendors, and improve supplier relationships. These agencies could train, mentor, and coach principals on identifying the best products in the market, adopting and deploying appropriate procurement technology, and improving procurement monitoring.

Recommendations Regarding Research Hypothesis 3

The MoE and other relevant agencies could train, mentor, and coach principals on detecting budget errors, adhering to budget plans, approving financial transactions, and authorising payments regularly. They can also train and coach them on segregating incompatible financial management duties, developing passwords to stop unauthorised access to financial management ICT systems and developing detective controls to prevent funds loss.

Recommendations Regarding Research Hypothesis 4

The MoE and other agencies should train, coach, and mentor principals and empower them with financial reporting competencies that can enable them to prepare reports that are free from material misstatement, errors, or bias; seek feedback on changes to report formats; and report to the BoM on budget status by generating standard financial reports. The MoE could encourage principals to improve the preparation of infrastructure project reports, reports to the BoM on school financial performance, and reports on creditors and payment due dates, as they share fee balances with the BoM.

Recommendations for Policy

1. The MoE, through the Directorate of Schools Audit Services (DSAS) and the TSC, should institute proper monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to support principals in complying with various financial management requirements.
2. The MoE and TSC should institute stringent policies, administrative actions, and sanctions against principals who do not comply with budgeting, procurement, internal financial control, and financial reporting requirements.
3. The MoE should implement systems and incentives that encourage the principals' voluntary compliance with budgeting, procurement, and implementation of internal financial controls and financial reporting laws, regulations, and guidelines.
4. Universities and colleges should infuse more financial management courses into pre-service and in-service teacher training programmes to expose teacher trainees and trained teachers to financial management to address the identified competency and skills gaps.

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